

Carbon sink role of lime-based construction units

Luciano Sambataro^{1*}, Neven Ukrainczyk¹, and Eduardus A.B. Koenders¹

¹Technical University of Darmstadt, Institute of Construction and Building Materials, 64287, Darmstadt, Germany

Abstract. This research quantifies the CO₂ uptake potential of lime-based construction units by TGA and LCA. Results show that CO₂ can be successfully stored in the bricks, decreasing their compressive strength and water absorption, and increasing their density.

Introduction

Around 430 million tonnes of lime are produced worldwide each year [1]. In parallel, similar amounts of CO₂ are emitted due to the chemical calcination process and the usage of fuel in the kiln [2]. Carbonation of lime-based construction units has been shown to potentially reduce a building's carbon footprint by 20% [3]. This research aims to quantify the potential use of CO₂ during industrial carbonation of Calcium Silicate Units (CSU) and Autoclaved Aerated Concrete (AAC).

Methodology

A combination of experimental research and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) modelling is proposed. First, CSB and AAC units are sized into 55x55x70 mm cubes. After drying the specimens at 105°C until constant mass, they are stored in a carbonation chamber with 50% relative humidity and 20% CO₂ concentration in air. The compressive strength, water absorption, and density are studied at 12 hours, 1, 7, 14, and 28 days. In addition, the carbonation degree is measured by means of TGA. For the LCA, a process-based modelling approach is followed in order to generate the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of both the CSU and the AAC. This is complemented with the impact assessment following the European Commission recommended method EF v3.1.

Results

Material characterisation

Table 1 displays the CSUs compressive strength (f_c), density (ρ), and water absorption (WA) results after different exposure times in the carbonation chamber. It can be seen that while the average compressive strength decreased by around 14%, there was an increase of 3.5% in density and an average decrease of 1.6% in water absorption.

Table 1: CSU properties after carbonation treatment

Exposure time	$f_{c_μ}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{c_σ}$ [N/mm ²]	$ρ_μ$ [kg/m ³]	$ρ_σ$ [kg/m ³]	$WA_μ$	$WA_σ$
Ref.: 0 h	27.1	1.2	1839.1	12.4	12.1%	0.3%

* Corresponding author: sambataro@wib.tu-darmstadt.de

12 h	27.1	1.7	1847.4	13.4	11.5%	0.2%
1 d	27.6	1.7	1869.3	7.8	11.1%	0.2%
7 d	27.3	1.8	1902.4	29.3	11.0%	0.5%
14 d	25.3	0.9	1892.5	16.7	11.0%	0.2%
28 d	23.3	0.5	1904.7	14.4	10.5%	0.1%

Carbonation degree

Results of the TGA, displayed in Figure 1, show an increase in the mass loss between 400°C and 800°C, with the increase of carbonation time. This can be attributed to the decomposition of calcite. Moreover, the initial difference between the outer layer and the core of the sample tends to equilibrate with time.

Figure 1. TGA results for the CSB at 0, 12 hours, and 7 days carbonation

Conclusions and outlook

This research proves the technical feasibility of mineral carbonation in CSUs and AAC blocks. Results show that the samples subjected to the rich CO₂ environment experienced a decrease in compressive strength and water absorption, and an increase in density. This may be attributed to the decomposition of tobermorite phases to form calcium carbonates. This could explain the difference in the mass loss shown in Figure 1. It should be stressed that the mechanical performance of the sample is still suitable for their structural purpose and, additionally, an increase in their long-term performance can be expected due to the lower permeability. The determination of the CO₂ footprint reduction by means of LCA will complement the experimental results.

This research has received funding support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions European Training Network – Innovative Training Network (ETN-ITN) under project acronym SUBLime and title: 'SUSTAINABLE BUILDING LIME APPLICATIONS VIA CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND BIOMIMETIC APPROACHES', Grant Agreement n°955986.

References

1. Statista. Lime production worldwide from 2010 to 2022. URL: www.statista.com/statistics
2. A. Laveglia, L. Sambataro, N. Ukrainczyk, E. Koenders, "Hydrated lime life-cycle assessment: Current and future scenarios in four EU countries". *JCP*, 369, Oct. 2022, 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133224
3. L. Sambataro, A. Laveglia, N. Ukrainczyk, E. Koenders. "A performance-based approach ...". *Energy and Buildings*, 295, Sept. 2023, 10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113287